

Results Based Management in Zimbabwe: Benefits and Challenges

A Conceptual Study

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Abstract: The public sector is now concerned with a focus on achieving more with fewer resources. Resources are shrinking and increasing demand for better quality results. There is an increasing need to improve efficiency and accountability for results. It is a global trend using Results Based Management to improve public sector performance. The governments world over have been experiencing scarcity of resources. In an effort to make use of scarce resources to improve public sector, the Government of Zimbabwe introduced Results Based Management in 2005 championed by a consultant from Malaysia where the management tool has been successful. The tool emphasised on achieving quality results with the use of limited resources. This paper seeks to examine the implementation of RBM approach in Government of Zimbabwe has faced, with successes, challenges and disappointments which have been documented and experienced.

I. Introduction

Two decades have elapsed and constant pressure is mounting on governments over the world to improve accountability and transparency as taxpayers become more concerned with the use of public resources (Gaebler, 1993; Aucoin, 1996). Escalation of public concern over decline confidence in leadership in political cycles, national account deficits and the need for accountability in governance and transparency are some of the factors that contributed to the emergence of RBM in the public sector. Several researchers have documented a new public sector management emergency approach now common in OECD countries. Traditionally governments have focused on financial, human and technical resources provided as inputs for programs. There has been a major shift in modern management agenda where the focus is on management in the public service that are expected to clearly define their results, be result oriented, performance measurement driven and be objective, performance evaluation and use the information for making any adjustments to come up with improved programmes (Canadian International Development Agency, 2005:2). Different governments have implemented Results Based Management systems with successes, challenges and disappointments' having been documented.

II. History of Results Based Management Systems

The concept of Results Based Management Systems is believed to have been put into initiation by Peter Drucker as Management By Objectives (MBO) and Program Performance Budgeting Systems (PPBS) in the 1960's and later developed into use a logical framework for public sector in the 1970's (Rassapan, 2003). United Nations Development

Program (2010) asserts that a valid Results Based Management System dwells on a life cycle where the outcome of goals rotate around planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluating, report presentation and continuous decision making. A focus outcome rather than activities insinuates the articulation of visions and giving support to obtain results and help in the monitoring of progress by use of indicators and set targets. Reports provided on the basis of results placed much focus on the organization and stakeholders to understand the impact of the Results Based Management Systems in a better way.

Different countries adopted Results Based Management Systems in the 1980's and 1990's using various names and developments have been encountered in an approach to improve effectiveness and efficiency in services provided. Components of the Results Based Management Systems have a view which dwells on results, measurements, an evaluation and the extent of accountability as tools essential for the achievement of more effective and efficient utilization of resources. Countries view the Results Based Management Systems as a tool that explains clear objectives of government towards service provision to the general public. Public service providers may lose sight of the purpose of their existence and they ignore the fact that they are there to serve the public. Results Based Management Systems exists as a tool which ensures an establishment and a clarification of the purpose of the organization, benefits and better still the impact it is supposed to make through the delivery of the services. Thomas (2005) explains that the systems used back then gave much emphasis and focus on resources without giving much detail on the implementation sector. The logical framework was used in the 1970s in a bid to track progress and it became of extensive use in the 1980s and 1990s as a tool of management. The adaptation and use of the framework program later evolved into versions which led to the evolution of the Results Based Management Systems.

Documentaries and researches previously worked on revealed that Results Based Management Systems was adopted due to the poor resource allocations, substandard service provision, poor service oriented personnel, limited funds, poor transparency and accountability in operations. Studies conducted by other academics proved that Results Based Management Systems assists policy makers track progress and provide demonstration of outcomes and impacts of an implemented system. Evidence of the success of Results Based Management Systems implemented in Malaysia, Uganda, South Korea and Australia explain that Results Based Management Systems provides a concise flow of information on realisation of practices (Madhekeni, 2012).

Major concentrations on aspects of presentation of results (outcomes and impacts) have played a role in the improvement of services and decision making. Results Based Management Systems is an initiative that gives much attention on the role of the government and its introduction is made easy with the availability of sufficient funds. The concept has also been adopted by internationally recognized donor agencies and the government of Zimbabwe introduced the aspect of Results Based Management Systems in 2005 through a document prepared by a Malaysian consultant.

III. Results Based Management Systems in Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe gained independence in 1980 and adopted and formulated a strategy focusing on reforming its public sector. The aim was at improving the delivery of the services so as to enhance the key national goals for development. (Office of the President and Cabinet, 2012). For the success of the achievement of the goals, public sector reforms were introduced which comprised of the Economic Structural Adjustment Programme (1991-1995), Zimbabwe Programme for Economic and Social Transformation (1996- 2000) and the Results Based Management Systems (2005 to date). The implementation of the Results Based Management Systems was in cooperation with the United Nations Development Program in 2005 (Office of the President and Cabinet, 2012). The goals of RBM was to promote the enhancement of efficiency, accountability and transparency and ensuring the improvement of delivery of services to meet developed targets (United Nations Development Program/ Office of the President and Cabinet/ Ministry of Finance, 2007). The success of the Results Based Management System was to be achieved through a strengthening tactic and capacity of the government entities to coordinate, plan, implement, budget and provide a link between the performance and results. Results Based Management System was a strategy meant to assist in the addressing of challenges which rose from pressures such as increasing demands of stakeholders, financial crisis and globalization.

The Government of Zimbabwe put in recognition the fact that a turn in the economy not only needed investments but an improvement in the efficiency of parastatals and the public sector. Targets under macro-economic sector that were negative could only be reversed through improved production especially in the manufacturing and mining sect,

agriculture and the introduction of the fiscal policies and inflation containment. These are the factors which contributed to a framework of the macro-economy which led to the implementation of the Results Based Management System.

An analysis of the International Monetary Fund led to the reinforcement of policies in the Government and the Senior Economic Adviser from Malaysia in 2005. The strategies led to a structural reform which was deemed comprehensive to reverse the Gross Domestic Product and the hyperinflation impeding effects it caused. The hyperinflation was caused by the agriculture sector weakening which resulted from the 'fast track' land reform, low amount of foreign exchange, reduced exports and the shortages in basic goods which comprise of food shortages, fuel and electricity which accumulated. This also affected humans in the sense that they were grain drained, diseases became prevalent and there was a sharp increase in child mortality. The need to restore the international relations became a great subject that was pointed out by the International Monetary Fund.

The Government of Zimbabwe upholds the Malaysian model but also recognizes the necessity of the Results Based Management System in enabling an enhancement of its value as a tool of management. Results Based Management System has become a strategy in the creation and transformation of an environment which restores the level of stability and growth. It is a force which supports, revamps levels of confidence in policies and forces an improvement in a country's image. Zimbabwe considered the Results Based Management System as a strategy that would bring about a united vision and high profits and anticipated change and modernization of activities in the state enterprises, central government, parastatals and local authorities.

Zinyama et al (2015) explains that Results Based Management System is a diversion of focus from inputs to outputs to provide a desire for tangible benefits and a final outcome. Results presented occur as effects of change on development and thus seek to give changes in the behaviours of the society which comprise of individuals, organizations and groups. Results Based Management System considers the organization culture, the set of values that are present and the decision making processes, skill and capacity of staff the stakeholders involved should put more effort on the making sure there is an achievement of outcomes that on input thus ensuring accountability and activity achievement.

The desire to improve levels of accountability and company transparency led to the application of Results Based Management System (Mutambatuwisi, 2016). The Results Based Management System as adopted by the government of Zimbabwe consists of five components namely the Integrated Development Planning (IDP), Results Based Budgeting (RBB), Results Based Personnel Performance System (RBPPS), Results Based Monitoring and Evaluation (RBM and E), Results Based Management Information Systems (RBMIS).

IV. Lead agencies in the implementation of Results Based Management Systems

- Ministry of Economic Planning and Investment Promotion – Integrated Development Planning
- Ministry of Finance and Economic Development – Results Based Budgeting
- Public Service Commission - Results Based Personnel Performance System, Results Based Monitoring and Evaluation and Results Based Management Information System
- Ministry of Public Service - implementation of Results Based Management Systems
- Ministry of Information, Communication & Technology – Result Based Management Information System
- The Office of the President and Cabinet (OPC) – Overall initiator of the Result Based Management System

Components of Result Based Management System

Integrated Development Plan (IDP)

Integrated development planning is a systematically structured approach to development plans comprising of an integration approach that is horizontal-vertical giving clear focus on the outcomes of the programme and its impact

(Rasappan, 2010). The strategy of Integrated Development Planning encompasses both national plans that are of importance and enabling that the priorities contribute to levels of a systematic manner.

According to Maphosa (2016) the aspect of planning encompasses objective formulation, indicator selection as measures of progress towards the goals and sets of challenging targets against each indicator so as to measure performance. The chain of results provides a facilitation of the operations in Results Based Management Systems and gives a link between inputs, processes and outputs, the outcomes and the impacts (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2002).

Results Based Budgeting (RBB)

Gwata (2013) explained that Results Based Budgeting is a management tool that is strategically set to provide an improvement in resource management thus improving accountability. Ministries gave presentations on the frameworks of performance which explained the annual outputs from budgets and the work plan detailing the outputs. A specification of the expected impact and outcomes was explained. The framework gave a basis for the agreement signed by the Permanent and Chief Secretary giving details that confirmed the ministry's commitment to ensure a spell out of the outputs for the year. The agreement became a tool of performance monitoring and managers made upload of information on a quarterly basis. Reports on performance were generated and they were monitored by the Ministry of Finance and the Office of the President and Cabinet. These reports gave much focus on application of input and completion of activities.

Results Based Personnel Performance System (RBPPS)

This component, which is directed by Public Service Commission (PSC), sought to improve delivery of services by ensuring an integration of the use of financial and human resources to ensure an achievement of desired results. Work plans were developed on the performance management agreement which was prepared under the Results Based Budgeting aspect. This highlighted that a provision of the much anticipated contribution was expected from the specified outputs and outcomes from each employee (Gwata, 2012)

Maphosa (2016) explains that the Results Based Personnel Performance System deals with the human aspect of performance management and focuses on the usage of human resources available to achieve the expected results. According to Thomas (2005), the performance of humans is seen as the major element in Results Based Management Systems (Rasappan, 2009) explains that Results Based Personnel Performance System provides facilities that ensure the performance management aspect of the organization. It is a useful tool which is used to drive initiatives. Appraisal systems under the performance system weigh the outcomes towards individual performance which can be linked to the framework of performance management.

Results Based Monitoring and Evaluation

Results Based Monitoring and Evaluation is a time framed approach that measures performance and it forms an integral part in the process of implementing Results Based Management Systems (Farell, 2009). Monitoring and Evaluation is a time framed assessment backed by a comprehensive Management Information System.

The Monitoring and Evaluation System, termed the Zimbabwe Integrated Performance Management Solution (ZIPMS) is managed by Office of the President and Cabinet (Gordon-Somers and Khosa, 2006). It consists of planning of the program, modules are monitored and reports are generated in time and accurate information is forwarded to the Ministry. Plans are done annually and are uploaded on the Zimbabwe Integrated Performance Management Solution, but output data is uploaded electronically to track progress. Quarterly performance reports are then generated from the reporting module.

Results Based Management Information System

The Results Based Management Systems and the Results Based Personnel Performance System, these two components provide the basis for performance planning by helping with the identification of the goals to be met. Monitoring the

programme to check if it's on track is a requirement in doing so necessary information is needed. Different information is needed at different levels and can be identified by the Management Information System (Thomas, 2005).

Rasappan (2009) views the Management Information System as a framework that shows information from the Monitoring and Evaluation System that assists management so that they can make informed decisions. Therefore the Management Information System is a basis for decision-making support system in the organisation at different levels.

Rasappan (2010) the Management Information Systems provides important information to support informed decision-making for programme improvement and adjustments to strategies and policies. The roles of the Management Information System and the Monitoring and Evaluation system are linked closely, they rely on each other ensuring that the right people receive the right information at the right time (Thomas 2005). The Management Information System can be planned and designed for manual use or for utilisation in computerised systems.

Results Chain

Source: Zimbabwe National Monitoring and Evaluation Policy 2015

United Nations Development Group (2012) explains that a result chain process reflects all needs, priorities and aspirations which desire to be accomplished by stakeholders. The factors associated encompass the economic, social, cultural, political and environmental aspects which are well known for affecting the presentation of results. The results chains vary from country to country whereas what may be an input in one country can be an outcome in another. Results chain encompasses a development sequence of interventions that stipulate the achievement of desired results. Inputs begin with the sequence moving to activities, outputs culminating in outcomes then lastly presentation of the impacts/goals and feedback

Inputs

Mutambatuwisi et al (2016) explains that the framework states that the most important aspect of the model is the development of inputs. Inputs associated with the framework comprise of capital, good infrastructure, human skills, labour force and the existence of strategic plan. Neely and Bourne (2002) explain that the success of all approaches to performance management are dependent on the presence of inputs to start and guide the performance of the organization. Inputs are actions performed which require inputs such as funds, technical assistance through training, human resources and associated resources for the production of specific outputs.

Activities

The framework recognises that processes or activities are not ends in themselves but means to an end. Harrington (1991) explains that for an effective model to be put into action, inputs add value to the commencement of activities and then give outputs to the customer. Results Based Management Systems considers processes as activities and make additions to value and deliver results of performance to stakeholders. They resemble procedural processes taken for the commencement of activities and procedures and access to processes guarantees efficient use of inputs. For instance, construction of infrastructure, feedback and reviews.

Outputs

Results Based Management Systems explains outputs as the number of percentages or other form of results which are a representative to the products of the process. The results provide an indication on the department which achieved set goals thus denoting the effectiveness of the performance model with recognition that organizational success is that which customers anticipate (Mutambatuwisi et al, 2016). The outputs are the desired products and services which result from the completion of activities within a development intervention. For example, product redesign, focus on employee activities and evaluation.

Outcomes

The welfare of the users has to be natured by the outputs thus there is a desire to present a follow up of the emanating results from the outputs to ensure there is a maximisation of public satisfaction. The results chain explains that the effectiveness of the model does not emanate from goals alone but from the extent of which the goals add value to public welfare (Heyer 2011). They explain the achieved short-term effects of the intermediation of outputs. The outcomes obtained represent the development changes that occur between completion of the output and the anticipated impact achievement. For example, more product lines are invented, increased geographical coverage and employees gain knowledge.

Impacts

Results Based Management Systems explains the impact as the long term aspect of the success of the model. According to (Thomas 2011), the performance approach explained under the public sector must provide positive impact on the environment it serves. This is widely explained in service delivery, the well-being of public sector and the other aspects adopted in the measurement of productivity. These encompass the positive long term effects on population groups that are presented by an intervention in a direct or indirect manner. The effects pose an impact on the external environment of the organization. For example, improvement in trade activities, increase in household income, positive environment which motivates people to work and contribution to the economic development.

Benefits of the Results Based Management Systems

Clarification of Goals and objectives

There is a clear outline of goals whereby employees create their own work plan and through a creation of the work plan, employees are responsible and present commitment towards their achievement. A clear pictorial of choices made through implemented goals and objectives can assist in the analysis of roadblocks during the process. Employees need an understanding of their work for the presentation of expectations. Contexts should be developed which comprise of an understanding of their position in the firm. This commences with the ability of the company and executive goals which acts as an intervention to manager, team and individual setting of goals. An alignment of workforce with extraordinary business goals helps the organization set priorities and direction and it ensures that individuals have ownership through achievement of objectives (Zvavahera, 2012)

Increase in Reward and recognition

Employees work extra hard to achieve set targets of activities and this will lead to superior performance whereby they present much effort in the execution of endeavours as focus dwells on results not processes. Training and staff development are regarded as the integral part of Results Based Management System. This enforces the fact that good performance is rewarded and substandard performance is worked on through training, development and other better ways which ensure success. Recognition assists employees in getting a balance in the positive and negative feedback. An unexpected appreciation can boost the morale of an employee. It goes beyond satisfying the fundamental needs, reinforces the expected behaviour and culture in the organizations behaviour and culture and enhances social engagement. Rewards and recognition improves retention of employees and enhances creation of the ambassadors for the organization and its culture (Zvavahera, 2012)

Improved communication

Since there is constant interaction between the supervisor and employee, performance management improves and the tasks are clearly defined and explained. Clarification of what is present at hand before the project begins and analysing the desired result before its accomplishment enables the implementers to maintain a good communication base which reduces the flow of information in an unambiguous manner (Gwata, 2013).

Development of capacity

Capacity development is instilled as the organization strives to ensure an environment which is clear and workable. This ensures clarification of our area of concentration, resources needed for the job and the real assumptions concerning the cause and effect of the strategy. Identification of intervention will enable strategic ways of establishing results. Employees that are motivated to perform work an extra mile when a positive experience is developed through interventions of performance management systems and management takes pride in employees that are eager to develop and grow professionally. There is need for organizations to analyse the effectiveness of their performance management systems and apply goals that have a link to initiatives of a strategic nature and strive to improve and achieve their mission (Madhekeni, 2012).

Consistency

Results Based Management Systems is associated with ensuring the achievement of set goals to reach to a certain goal. This entails having the right person at the right job since they have knowledge on what they are doing (Bester, 2006). Ongoing training and establishment of a communication base on both employees and managers ensures the success of a set of expectations about performance and the ratings associated. Management and their employees should share an understanding on the performance scales so as to achieve high levels of consistency and fairness in employee performance reviews.

Realistic project schedules are set

Planning that is not vague presents real schedules thus providing an analysis of thought towards planning and monitoring for effective evaluations. Priorities are recognized which ensures presentation of end results on time and it reduces idleness of the employees as they know they are working towards a certain defined goal (Beister, 2010).

Culture enhancement

Results Based Management System spruces up the ability of an organization to develop a culture whose main focus is on results presentation (Epstein and Olsen, 1996). Wachira (2013) emphasizes that Results Based Management Systems entails the implementation of change management measures so as to instil major shifts in the mind set of carrying out businesses. A shift from the administrative culture to a Results Based Management System culture establishes a focus on the presentation of relevant inputs and expected outputs to ensure a provision of quality services. Culture change is a long process but for the success of the Results Based Management System, there is need to be consistent, perseverance and ensure extensive monitoring.

Obstacles in implementing Results Based Management Systems

Existing culture

An effective implementation of Results Based Management Systems depends on the ability of the organization to develop a culture of management that has its focus fixed on results. (United States General Accounting Office 1997). Strategies of diversion of the culture face resistance as it is hard for individuals to adopt approaches that cause changes in the organizational behaviour (Mayne, 2007). The obvious reasons for inability to adopt the change is that the organizations have a usual way of carrying out endeavours, satisfaction with status quo and thus they are not motivated to improve performance (Amjad, 2003). Senior management may not be interested in the diversion of business management and this leads to a failure in adopting its usefulness.

Importation of Results Based Management Systems models of operation

Col et al (2006) explains that organizations fail to recognize that certain technologies of management cannot be transferred to the new organization structure because all countries have a history, political structure that is ideal, the priorities differ and different core resources which are not recognized by consultants. Significantly, Amjad (2003) is against the idea of adaptation of the imported models from countries that are developing while Curristine et al (2010) provides suggestions that Results Based Management Systems strategies should be implied so as to meet specified objectives.

Lack of incentives

Performance improvement in organizations cannot flourish without the incentives directly linked with employee performance. (World Bank, 2003). Financially designated incentives seek to reward employees who perform well and this is a strategy to improve motivation so as to attain much higher levels of performance (Eyben, 2013). Monetary or non-monetary categorized incentives can be given at both organizational and individual level (Ortiz, 2004; World Bank, 2011). Attractive as it might sound to link performance of an employee to monetary rewards, there is the aspect of implementation which is deemed difficult and complex (Dan, 2009) explains that there is vagueness associated with the issue of financial incentives which leads to presentation of distorted information as one seeks to present information that will ensure they get an incentive. Organizational cultures which put emphasis on teamwork may have influence on the individuals in an organization.

Setting unrealistic expectations

The United Nations Development Programme (2010) details the aspect of setting unrealistic goals and expectations that do not follow the SMART criteria to link them to results. Meier (2000) explains that over-complexity has been seen as one of the risky factors that threaten the implementation of Results Based Management Systems whereby the targets set could be low or high. Targets that are highly set could motivate the organization but they could also create expectations that are not real which could lead to organizational failure (Curristine 2005a).

The problem of failing to get buy-in and use of the system

Implementation of Results Based Management Systems in the developing countries is a strategy established in association with high costs which include large injections of money and time. Success of Results Based Management Systems is hindered by the inability to plan and align systems and lack of experience which in turn has implications on the buy-in and the use of Results Based Management Systems. (The CGIAR A Strategy and Results Framework Management Update, 2013 - 2014.) .Continuous monitoring and performance are essential for the success of Results Based Management Systems. Madhekeni (2012) and the Economic Commission for Africa (2003) move with the same notion that most African governments have no institutional capacity because of the decline in developments and the economically related constraints which comprise of human and finances. These factors have hindered the training of employees so as to become knowledgeable about the Results Based Management Systems.

The problem of setting outcome expectations

According to Bester (2012), organizations have the capacity to define output levels yet the Results Based Management Systems requires companies to have a vision of operating beyond the defined output. (Perrin, 2002; Boyne & Law, 2005) pin point that many organizations have a challenge of establishing outcome expectations on the expected performance. The challenge of selecting relevant performance information and using it in decision-making

The large amount of information provided by the Results Based Management Systems can easily be flooded on the users resulting on the lack of ability to be selective in the process. (Williamson, 2003). As such, Mayne (2007) states that information overload has caused a failure in the implementation of the Results Based Management Systems. The World Bank (2011) states that due to its designed way of a large amount of information, it takes a long time to ensure that the organization has selected and determined which data would be of relevance in collecting.

The problem of distorting behaviour

Organisations that give much focus on output usually end up with displacement of goals which lead to organizational cheating. Results Based Management Systems gives much focus on the output of the organization thus the organizations aim at ensuring that their outcome of activities is successful (Curristine et al. 2008; Curristine 2005a). When an organization implements Results Based Management Systems, there are chances that they could be faced with unrealistic demands and poor resources to ensure it is deemed a success thus goal displacement presents an imposter image of what is actually happening (Bohte & Meier, 2000).

The problem of accountability for outcomes

According to Saldanha (2002), factors that restrict the performance of public sector is the weak accounting systems and worse still their non-existence which provide a focus on the management of input and activity rather than on the outcome management. Economic and social shifts may make management feel uncomfortable where focus dwells much on outcomes influenced by activities they are not able to control (Mayne, 2007). Such factors include economic and social changes. According to Curristine et al. (2008), the outcomes may be complex and can result in the inclusion of characteristics of planned and unplanned factors.

Employees' perceptions on Results Based Management Systems

Buchner (2007) explained in his researches that employees have bad feelings over the adaptation of the Results Based Management Systems in their organizations. Some employees after being consulted explained how the system overpowers employees and gives no recognition to their efforts. Studies conducted by academics provide ample evidence that when well explained, implemented and adapted to, the Results Based Management Systems technique becomes of great importance leading to engagement of employees with their work.

DeNisis and Pritchard (2006) allude that the behaviour presented by employees towards the implementation of goals and activities has a great effect on output. Attitudes toward performance management affect the performance of employees in organisation. Mandishona (2003) states that the survival of an organization and its flourishing can only be guaranteed once employees grasp and have a positive approach to the system as a whole. A win-win situation whereby the employees and managerial sect, the organisation and good service delivery is dependent on how employees perceive the whole system.

A clear relationship between the employer and employees where a common goal is reached thus providing satisfaction and relatable outcome towards activities. There is need thus to let organizations ensure there is a strong link tied to performance and benefits provided to ensure positive insinuations towards the organization goals.

V. Lack of training

Employees were not aware of the Results Based Management Systems because it was not fully and well implemented and this poses a threat to the presentation of results. The employees just signed circulars on the transition from the previously used performance management technique to the Results Based Management Systems and they were not trained for the Results Based Management Systems. This factor becomes a threat to the success of the Results Based Management Systems as it requires training for its commencement. There are no adequate resources for the implementation of the Results Based Management Systems thus increasing the idleness of human labour instead of presentation of results and improved output.

United Nations Development Group (2010) explains that as management system becomes results based, it is assumed that the implementation process shall yield better lessons, adjustments and make decision making a success. The essence of continuous feedback seeks to establish more projects and programmes that are responsive to the relevant environments. United Nations Agencies and country teams ensure that they have mechanisms for flexibility which accommodate adjustments and learning thus they work in conjunction with the governments. This unity enhances the utilization of meetings, periodic reviews and they establish room for questions, provision of technological information and assistance which facilitates exchange of knowledge.

Thomas (2007) explains that the Results Based Management Systems has brought about a shift in the economic and competitive sector of the East African region through efficient management of the public services and the

entrepreneurial spirits of the private sector. Results Based Management Systems is a management approach which has enabled economies to experience success. Ninety six percent of the relevant goals of Malaysia have been successful through planning strategically, measuring and reporting and the systematic approach to the use of information. It gives emphasis on the importance of presentation of results through systematically set goals and objectives thus creating apposite environment which yields results.

Conclusion

Zimbabwe's experience with Results Based Management Systems like many other African countries has exposed more negative than positive results although the Results Based Management Systems initiation is considered valid for improving performance in the public sector and is also a vital tool for the program and project management in the government. It must not be termed complicated for a country that is developing to undertake. This study recognizes the crucial importance of the role of Results Based Management Systems in ensuring a match between the inputs and outputs of the chain. It also acknowledges the fact that with an ineffective Results Based Management Systems it is difficult to be associated with meaningful and well-informed processes of decision making inclusive of policy and management levels of state agencies. The RBM tool has been implemented in Zimbabwe since 2005 but results are yet to be realised and it has been marred by more challenges than successes.

The Zimbabwean government investment in the implementation of RBM should be quite sizeable in both inputs and activities, and the return on investment will be quite valuable. Though there are challenges being faced in the implementation of RBM in Zimbabwe its importance as a management tool to improve public sector performance remains vital.

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